

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF MECHANICALLY FASTENED JOINTS IN CFRP

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SUMMARY: The effects of friction and clearance on the stress distribution around a hole in a mechanically fastened joint are investigated using a three-dimensional finite element model. The effects of these parameters are assessed by comparison with the perfect-fit, frictionless case. The influence of friction and clearance on the stress concentration factors related to bearing and tension failures, on the position of the maximum stresses and on the contact angle are investigated. It is concluded that with increasing friction, the maximum radial stress decreases whereas the maximum hoop stress increases. The locations where the maximum values occur are also influenced by the presence of friction. These effects may influence both strength and failure mode. The presence of clearance increases the maximum radial stress at the bearing plane and the maximum hoop stress at the end of the contact. It is concluded that a clearance fit reduces the joint strength.

KEYWORDS: joining, mechanical fastening, friction, clearance, finite element method

INTRODUCTION

Mechanically fastened joints have a wide range of applications in aeronautical industry. Typical applications in aircraft are the skin to spar connections in a wing, wing to fuselage connection and tail to fuselage connection. Although design procedures are well established to join metallic parts, the complex behavior of composite laminates and the possibility of choosing between several material combinations demands further research. As a joint is a critical component in a structure, improved designs are required to avoid a significant weight penalty. It was found [1-7] that factors like joint geometry, fibre orientation, stacking sequence and through-thickness pressure are important parameters on the joint strength. To include all these factors in a detailed stress analysis, required before predicting strength, numerical methods are adequate. In order to deal with the three-dimensional stress state at the hole boundary, the effects of stacking sequence and through-thickness pressure, three-dimensional models have been proposed [8], [9]. Such models are quite adequate when predicting bearing failure mode, where three-dimensional effects are extremely important [9], [10]. In this work, the effects of friction and clearance between the pin and the hole on the stress distributions around a pin-loaded hole in carbon-fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) are investigated using a three-dimensional finite element model. The model is validated using an analytical solution derived for an infinite plate [11]. The stress distributions and stress concentration factors obtained for clearance fits and contacts with friction between the pin and the laminate are then compared with the frictionless, perfect-fit model. The present model will be developed in the future to include strength and failure mode prediction.

MODEL VALIDATION

In order to assess the accuracy of the finite element model, a comparison was made with the results obtained using de Jong's [11] analytical solution. A quasi-isotropic $(0^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ CFRP laminate is modelled using a three-dimensional finite element model. The material properties used are: $E_{11}=146.90$ GPa, $E_{22}=E_{33}=10.89$ GPa, $G_{12}=G_{13}=6.41$ GPa, $G_{23}=3.89$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=0.38$ and $\nu_{23}=0.78$. ABAQUS' [12] three-dimensional eight-node isoparametric laminated brick elements were used to model the laminate. Due to symmetry, only half of the laminate was modelled and the loading pin is assumed rigid. The laminate is clamped along one edge and a displacement is given to the rigid pin. A frictionless contact between the pin and the hole is assumed. The contact zone is calculated and a perfect-fit connection between the pin and the hole is modelled.

A FORTRAN program was created in order to process ABAQUS [12] results. The stresses at the hole boundary nodes are transformed from the material axes of each layer to a cylindrical coordinate system and the average stress at each position is calculated. These stresses are then normalized using the bearing stress, S_b , defined as:

$$S_b = \frac{P}{dt} \quad (1)$$

P being the load applied to the joint, t the laminate thickness and d the hole diameter.

The circumferential co-ordinate direction θ and the planes associated with the principal failure modes are defined in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Definition of planes and angle θ

The distribution of the normalized radial and hoop stresses along the hole boundary obtained by the current model and by the analytical solution [11] are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Comparison of results

It can be seen that a good agreement between the finite element model and the analytical solution is achieved. Note that these distributions are independent of pin displacement.

EFFECT OF FRICTION

The same laminate configuration was used to verify the effect of friction on the stress distribution around pin-loaded holes. Three coefficients of friction, 0.2, 0.4 and 0.6, are used and the results are compared with the previous (frictionless) model.

The isotropic Coulomb friction model was used on the bolt-hole contact surface. The contact surfaces will slide when the following relation is satisfied:

$$\sigma_{r\theta} \geq \mu \sigma_{rr} \quad (2)$$

μ being the coefficient of friction between the pin and the laminate and σ_{rr} and $\sigma_{r\theta}$ the radial and shear stress respectively.

Small sliding between the pin and the hole is assumed. This means that a given node at the hole boundary will interact with the same local surface of the pin during the loading. Using this procedure, instead of verifying the contact between a node at the hole boundary and the entire surface of the rigid pin, the model is computationally more efficient and physically realistic.

The normalized radial, hoop and shear stress distributions along the hole boundary are shown in Fig. 3, Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 respectively.

Fig. 3: Normalized radial stress distribution along the hole boundary

Fig. 4: Normalized hoop stress distribution along the hole boundary

Fig. 5: Normalized shear stress distribution along the hole boundary

Increasing friction reduces the maximum radial stress and moves the location where the maximum occurs away from the bearing plane. The stress gradient along the hole boundary is also smaller when friction increases. The opposite effect occurs in the distribution of the hoop stress. It can be seen from Fig. 4 that the maximum hoop stress increases with increasing friction. The place where the maximum occurs is not significantly affected by the friction. The hoop stress near the bearing plane changes from tension to compression with increasing coefficient of friction. The angle where the compressive hoop stress occurs increases from 15° to 30° when the coefficient of friction increases from 0.4 to 0.6. As expected, the shear stress along the hole boundary increases with increasing coefficient of friction and the position of maximum shear stress moves away from the bearing plane (Fig. 5).

Stress concentration factors K_{bb} and K_{tb} are defined as:

$$K_{bb} = \frac{(\sigma_{rr})_{max}}{S_b} \tag{3}$$

$$K_{tb} = \frac{(\sigma_{\theta\theta})_{max}}{S_b} \tag{4}$$

The effects of friction on K_{bb} and K_{tb} and on the positions where these coefficients occur are shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7.

Fig. 6: Effect of μ on K_{bb}

Fig. 7: Effect of μ on K_{tb}

The values of K_{bb} decrease in absolute value from -1.18 to -0.71, for coefficients of friction of 0 and 0.6 respectively. The position of maximum K_{bb} moves from $\theta=0^\circ$ to $\theta=54^\circ$. For the same coefficients of friction, K_{tb} increases from 0.87 to 1.15, but the position of the maximum value only changes by 4.5° , from 85.5° to 90° .

In Fig. 8, the sliding and non-sliding zones are shown for the several coefficients of friction.

Fig. 8: Sliding zones and contact angles for several values of μ

As expected, the arc where sliding occurs decreases with increasing friction. The contact angle, ϕ , increases from 85° (frictionless situation and for $\mu=0.2$ and 0.4) to 90° ($\mu=0.6$).

EFFECT OF CLEARANCE

The effect of clearance was assessed by comparison of the results obtained from the perfect fit model with the results of a model including the minimum clearance value prescribed by prEN Aerospace 6037 standard (7/95 draft; clearance of 0.0127 mm) [13]. A rigid pin and a frictionless contact were assumed.

The normalized radial and hoop stresses around the hole boundary are shown in Fig. 9 for both configurations. For the model including clearance, the results are shown for several displacements of the pin: 2, 4 and 10% of the hole diameter.

Fig. 9: Stress distributions for perfect-fit and clearance

The presence of clearance increases the normalized radial and normalized hoop stresses near the bearing plane and at the end of the contact arc respectively. At the bearing plane, the presence of clearance decreases the normalized hoop stress. These trends are reduced when the displacement of the pin is increased and, consequently, when the contact angle increases. This is further shown in Fig. 10 where the relation between K_{tb} , K_{bb} and the displacement of the pin is shown. The contact angles (ϕ) are also shown in Fig. 10 and defined in Fig. 8.

Fig. 10: Relation between displacement, K_{tb} and K_{bb}

The non-linear relation between the contact angle and applied load is shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11: Relation between displacement and contact angle

Both stress concentration factors K_{tb} and K_{bb} increase with the presence of clearance. These factors decrease for high pin displacements, but never reach the values obtained with a perfect-fit. Such results are related to the reduction of the contact angle shown in Fig. 11.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results obtained we can conclude that friction has a significant effect on the stress distribution around a pin-loaded hole, and consequently on the strength of a mechanically fastened joint. The most significant effect of friction is the reduction of the maximum radial stress and the change in location of the maximum away from the bearing plane. The reduction of the maximum radial stress can improve the bearing strength but the variation of position at the hole boundary where it occurs can change both damage mechanisms and bearing strength. The hoop stress near the bearing plane is reduced and becomes compressive for high coefficients of friction. This effect should not have significant influence on the bearing strength. The maximum hoop stress increases, but the position where it occurs is not significantly affected. Such effect is undesirable in joints prone to tensile failures. As expected, the shear stress increases with increasing friction, and friction increases the contact angle slightly. These effects may influence both strength and failure mode, so reliable methods to determine coefficient of friction between a metallic pin and a laminate are required, and a model to predict the strength of this type of joint should take into account the effect of friction.

The presence of clearance between the pin and the hole increases the maximum radial stress at the bearing plane and the maximum hoop stress at the end of the contact. Considering that these stresses are related to bearing and tension failures respectively, we can conclude that a clearance fit leads to a reduction of the joint strength. With this type of fit the relation between the contact angle and applied load is non-linear and the contact angle is less than the contact angle for a perfect fit. If we also consider that clearance reduces fatigue life of mechanically fastened joints in CFRP, we can conclude that such fits should be avoided.

Comprehensive information about effects on the load-carrying capability of the joint can be obtained if a strength prediction method is included in the present model. The current model will be developed in order to predict failure and failure mode using progressive damage laws based on experimental observations. As the stress concentration factors depend on the lay-up

used and joint geometry, the influence of friction and clearance will be assessed in laminates with other lay-ups and finite dimensions. In order to improve the predictions of the through-thickness stresses, new finite element models using three-dimensional elements in each layer of the laminate will be created.

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